

>> **Aether Unification**(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m8K7xY-IKSw>)

In this letter:

- A review (as was requested) of Ken's theories on the UAF
- A discussion of PEMC vs. Ken's Tesla-Dollard-Steinmetz-Heaviside distillation
- Corrections to Ken's hypotheses

Theoria Apophasis: the Ken Wheeler¹ Effect

A refutation of the elaborate complexification and inconsumerability of a theory that tries to exist without plasma. Where we agree and where we disagree.

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Best view at: <https://bit.ly/3y7kr5E>

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/k-wheeler>

*“The great Way is not named,
the great disagreement is unspoken,
great benevolence is not benevolent,
great modesty is not humble,
great courage is not violent.
The Tao that is clear is not the Tao,
speech which enables argument is not worthy,
benevolence which is ever present does not achieve its goal,
modesty if flouted, fails,
courage that is violent is pointless.”²*

“Kung Sun Lung asked Mou of Wei, ‘When I was younger, I learned the Tao of the earlier kings, and as I grew up, I saw clearly the significance of benevolence and righteousness. I brought together difference and similarity, discerned hardness and whiteness, what was certain and what was not, what was possible and what was not. I laboured at understanding the Hundred Schools of Philosophy and spoke out against their teachings. I thought I had understanding of all things. Now, however, I have heard the words of Chuang Tzu, and to my surprise I am disturbed by them. Is it that my knowledge is not as good as his, or is it that his understanding is greater? I find I can’t even open my mouth, so I ask you what I can do.’

Duke Tzu Mou leaned forward, sighed heavily, looked to Heaven, smiled and said, ‘Dear Sir, have you not heard of the frog in the broken-down old well? He said to the turtle of the Eastern Ocean, “I have a great time! I leap on to the well wall, or I go down in the well, stepping along the broken bricks. When I enter the water, I float with it supporting my chin, feet up; on the mud, I dig my feet deep in. I look about me at the larvae, crabs and tadpoles and there is none that is as good as I. To have complete control of the waters of the gorge and not to wish to move but to enjoy the old well, this is great! Dear Sir, why don’t you come down and see me sometime?”

‘The turtle of the Eastern Ocean tried, but before he had put his left foot into the well, his right knee was stuck. At this he paused, shuffled out backwards and then began to speak about the ocean. “A distance such as a thousand miles doesn’t come close to describing its length, nor a depth of a thousand leagues describe its deepness. In the time of Yu, nine years in every ten there were floods, but this did not raise the ocean an inch. In the time of Tang, seven years in every eight there were droughts, but this did not lower the ocean shore an inch. Nothing changes these waters, neither in the short term nor in the long term; they neither recede nor advance, grow larger nor smaller. This is the great happiness of the Eastern Ocean.”

When the frog in the broken-down old well heard this, he was utterly amazed and astonished; he was utterly astonished, dumbfounded and at a loss.”³

² Chuang Tzu, Ch. 2 <https://terebess.hu/english/tao/ChuangTzu-palmer.pdf>

³ Ibid. Ch. 17

Re: Does Ken's UAF concept provide more simplicity or complicate the discussion of the PEMF (or for him the dielectric force)?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

It's an interesting thing to be from the same city (Lexington, Kentucky) as my esteemed colleague and co-alumnus, and have never met him, physically. Indeed we have interacted, as you might suspect, but only daetherically (via email, as it were). Nevertheless I do extend (always) an invitation to Mr. Wheeler to speak with me - dialogue if you will, debate if you must - the nature of the Unified Aether Field.

In a previous work⁴ I have deciphered the mystery of the Aether, though I admit I do not (and postulate no one does) have an anatomy of that Aether, but that it is composed of neutrino type particles and the like, perhaps more fine or less fine, by varying degrees, and probably to include baryons⁵. Nevertheless I identified in my Magnum Opus (at that time) "Magnetic Universe Theory" that the UAF *is* the PEMF, the Plasma-electromagnetic Force, a unification of the three nuclear scale forces, and ignoring gravity as a mere (as Thornhill^{6 7} and Velikovskiy⁸ identified) property of charge and distance⁹. Perhaps there is attraction, perhaps objects are pushed together, no one rightly knows. Nevertheless, I postulated that the PEMF was Serpienzki-like fractal, that it merely appears different at different scales and zoom factors, and that R. Distinti¹⁰ had identified the imaginary number¹¹ and this proved the reasoning behind the "right hand rule". Additionally he had improved the precision of the EMF Heaviside/Maxwell equations, but also shown that in fact eddies would be endless (theoretically) and therefore the PEMF was not only fractal in a self-replication sense, but also in an infinite sense.

I postulated that because the electromagnetic "waves" need no specific other medium to propagate that was (as of yet) found, but that clearly they must need something, then the PEMF was the UAF everyone had been looking for. This is a triquetra unification which respects the mytho-historical-alchemical-astrological past and unifies our religious origins¹² with our natural philosophae¹³ and scientific origins. Therefore, in a way the Velikovskians were right¹⁴. Later, by following the paradigm to its scientific maxims I showed that even they had underestimated the

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https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

⁵ Roughly half of all "dark matter"

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YkWiBxWieQU&t=2019s>

⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/thunderbolts-project/w-thornhill>

⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/velikovskiy>

⁹ What Ken is calling a 'sub variant' (basically we agree).

¹⁰ Ibid. pp. 39-60

¹¹ "Vortrix Algebra," R. Distinti, 2019

¹² https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

¹³ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

truth, and indeed the Chinese were not merely being Fibonacci¹⁵, but literal when they described that “the one begat the two, the two begat the three, and the three begat the ten-thousand myriad things.” They were describing Pangu’s Egg¹⁶, and the cosmic egg¹⁷ was IsRaEl / Shamazh/ Zurvan / Anu / Osiris / Indra - a dwarf star¹⁸ (red or brown is not yet known for certain) which split into proto-Saturn¹⁹, proto-Jupiter²⁰, and Neptune. Later these went about their ways and because of charge, and momentum considerations²¹ as the solar system entered Sol’s electric field, they were stratified into their various places. Saturn ejected Venus²², which then had cataclysmic results in exchange with Mars²³, etc. This is all detailed, rote, elsewhere. But the foundations of the discussions in the “On the Origins of Religions” and “Plasmaglyphs, Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction” papers, were contained in this **central idea**.

Now Ken (I believe I can call you Ken, since we are basically electro-brothers), you have said “Mother Nature is simple,” and I agree with you. As you can see in my work that shows Light is most definitely **not a particle**²⁴ (not sure why you have said it is in this new video), I credit you for *illuminating* my mind that *c* is the rate of induction of the *perturbation* of light in the aetheric field. Fine. Let me tell you, light is a counter-rotational, polarized (by the 90 degree out of phase conglomerate construction of electromagnetism) Birkeland structure. The imaginary number is defined by Distinti²⁵, and you can read more in my “Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis”²⁶ about that, but in essence, there is a rotation of the binary values of 0, 1, and -1, such that the wave structure is self-contained, and coaxial. Therefore the circuit is coaxial (and you agree), and not two waves alternating at 90 degrees. Nevertheless, the Lorentz Force is a 90 degree rotation. However, you sir have claimed that there is no magnetism (as in attraction), no one has defined the field, and that electricity is the meeting of magnetism (?) with dielectricity, a word formed as a non-polarization of electricity (which is polar)! How confusing are these ideas, they strain credulity.

Firstly, the PEM force is a simplification of complexity, and therefore a simplex concept. It is a venn diagram²⁷ that allows us to study many seemingly different phenomena, and make predictions. You claimed once no one could solve your puzzle, but Distinti did, with surface and edge currents²⁸ in the magnets²⁹. We know that electric “flux” actually occurs on the surface and

¹⁵ https://www.academia.edu/49945675/Basic_chinese_cosmology

¹⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pangu>

¹⁷

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/70768047/Shamash_Proto_Saturn_OpEd

¹⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

²⁰ “Jupiter Myth,” J. West, 2018

²¹ “On the Cosmogony of the Solar System,” H. Alfven, 1976 (3 parts)

<https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/h-alfven>

²² <https://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html> #66-68

²³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

²⁴ https://www.academia.edu/72712372/OpEd_Light_photons_Cannot_Possibly_be_a_Real_Particle

²⁵ Ibid. pp.5

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

²⁷ And in linear algebra all [data sets] have (contexts of reality)

²⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9sUP_iL6NIU

²⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fgHfW8fqqXI>

not as droplets in a copper pipe³⁰. So therefore I think his solving your puzzle bears mention. Also the fact that his aether particles and vortices match Weber's³¹ electrodynamical model³², which *preceded* Maxwell, Faraday, Tesla etc. is incredibly important. How can you seriously assert there is dielectric, and say the electric is after/sub-variant? The Law of Polarity is applied across all stratifications, no matter what. You cannot eliminate the south pole to support the north pole, that has no meaning! It is like saying there is beautiful, but no ugly, or up, but no down.

Then to say that magnetism is not attraction really strains credulity when all of the physics community has demonstrated attraction of the poles for hundreds of years back to Gilbert³³. This is not like gravity where you can plainly see that the only things happening are falling towards the Earth but not towards one another, one can hold the magnets and feel the attraction. There is attraction because a field **has a definition and it is that a field is a relationship**. I have shown, rote, that the western use of the word "field" can be likened to the Chinese concept of the word, which is plasmaglyphic and related to the Saturnian glyph, first as a "maltese" cross formation, then hexagonal.³⁴ The south pole of Saturn is a hexagon and this is a Birkeland Current. The Chinese were aware of the field's relationship to Dao/Tao, and to the great Force that was controlling and unifying the solar system, and Universe. Therefore, it was the Chinese (or first Egyptians/Atlantians) who first unified the field!

Now, do you suppose that the builders of the Great Pyramid power plant³⁵, who were attracting the Birkeland Currents (shown in PEM terrella lab experiments, co-extant with Tesla and Heaviside, etc.) at the 30° N point at Giza with electrum alloy, for use in generating the electric field to light their own Dendera Bulbs were interested in the *dielectric* or the *electric*? They were interested in the electric as has been everyone. Therefore to say that electricity isn't the point really strains the mind of the straightforward thinker. We are interested in the superconductive³⁶ phase because of the magnetic phase locking that occurs, and the disintegration of the impedance (resistance becomes 'zero'), particularly because of the conductance. If there is no resistance, there must be some approach to infinite conductance. Does one conduct dielectricity or magnetism³⁷? No. Therefore we are interested in the RLC behaviors of light and of 'electrons' (whatever they are) because the conveyance of energy is the point, not the aside. The magnetism follows the electricity by 90 degrees phase, and we can measure the electricity of the "black hole" 'jets' which are neither objects nor jets ('faucets') but Birkeland Currents arising out of Marklund-Lerner-Bennet pinches (Z pinches for short) in a Bostickian Super Plasmoid (BSP). Classical Black Holes are non-existent³⁸, they are already debunked. What magnetism appears to "flow" out is merely the following current of the 90-degree counter-rotation of electricity.

³⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iph500cPK28>

³¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/weber>

³² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models>

³³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/mag-universe/gilbert>

³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

³⁵ "Giza Power Plant," C. Dunn, 1998

<https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/c-dunn>

³⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/mag-universe/superconductivity>

³⁷ Magnetic flux is a mathematical concept, only.

³⁸ https://www.academia.edu/38152014/Neutrinos_Neutron_Stars_and_Axions_pdf

EPEMC :: Opinion Editorial
Unified Aether Field Series

You have also said there is no electric force by itself, but we have created and measured electric fields. Any child can hold a bulb outside the plasma orb and light it like Tesla. I have an entire paper on the changes in electric fields after treatments of my patients, whereas their magnetism did not alter one bit.³⁹ Therefore we can, actually, isolate them, though they are part and parcel of the same unification. This happens because the first polar relationship is matter and force (plasma-EM), then within the force (electro-magnetism), and then within each of these (electric, dielectric, magnetic, and diamagnetic). These, as you know, also have poles. Polar Complete Physics⁴⁰, as first discussed by the Chinese and later by Capra and Holbrook follows the Fibonacci sequence and the Laws (*P* power), which are forward and backwards applicable:

0 1 1 2 | 3 5 8 13

There are 8 laws. But our observation of the One Law (causality personified in the Force/*F* power) is seen through the asymptote of the Law of Polarity, and therefore we see the 1 as 3 ($0+1+1=2$; $1+2=3$).

Therefore, your desire to reduce to one is admirable, but doomed to “cut off the nose despite the face.” The reality is that you cannot really reduce any of it any furthermore than it has been. The proof of this is as I said about the Magnetic Universe people⁴¹, you end up with a word salad of complications and talking about inconsumerability, and focusing upon the “this is it” and “that is it.” Saying it is simple while making it sound incredibly complex, is another proof of the fractal nature discussed in PEMF theory: it always looks different depending on scale and zoom, and the differences (by rule of polarity) are both **real and illusory**.

We really can isolate electric fields or magnetic fields, but the division is our delusion-illusion stemming from ignorance and mortal-finitivity. The Hindus call this dukkha and maya, ignorance/suffering and illusion.

But while it is all one, and not in a Hippy/New Age way but in a Tesla sort of way, there is the plain fact that one must divide to study It All. Derivation and integration are polarities. Your attempts to provide a unification are thwarted by the very forces you propose to simplify.

Now that I have replied to this, and explained *why* you require the word-salads, I'll respond, as per your request directly to the image you have provided:

³⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases

⁴⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/quantum/polar-complete-physics>

⁴¹

https://www.academia.edu/73271902/Paradigm_Shift_Comparison_EPEMC_vs_The_Rest_Comparing_PEMC_EU_PU_MU_and_SM_BSM

Figure 1 - Ken's Unified Field Theory; credit: K. Wheeler⁴²

Breakdown of Ken's Theory

Unfortunately, he has not provided numbers for each point, so I will be writing top-left to bottom-right.

1. "PRIMORDIAL CONJUGATE FIELD: *Magnetism is toroidal Aether-rarefaction*"
 - a. Toroid is donut-shaped; magnetism may or may not shape as a toroid, but in general I am not in disagreement here.

Figure 2 - a torus; credit: Wiki

- b. Rarefaction: "*diminution in the density of something, especially air or a gas.*"
So his assertion here is that magnetism is the density of the Aether. But that is most definitely charge, so is he saying magnetism is charge? Remember, in PEMC we say that the root of all UAF/PEMF is **charge**. All of it is charge. But charge is polar, you cannot establish a charge value except in relation to another pole or value. There is no 0 ground, it's just Earth's charge.⁴³
2. "*Fundamental force & the dielectric-field (in loss of inertia). Centrifugal force & motion which both creates space and resultant dielectric torsion ('gravity')*"
 - a. Oh here we go. What does he mean by fundamental? How is one force more or less fundamental? Undefined (in his meaning).
 - b. Dielectric field: "*dielectric, insulating material or a very poor conductor of electric current. When dielectrics are placed in an electric field, practically no current flows in them because, unlike metals, they have no loosely bound, or free, electrons that may drift through the material. Instead, electric polarization occurs. The positive charges within the dielectric are displaced minutely in the direction of the electric field, and the negative charges are displaced minutely in the direction opposite to the electric field. This slight separation of charge, or polarization, reduces the electric field within the dielectric. The presence of dielectric material affects other electrical phenomena. The force between two electric charges in a dielectric medium is less than it would be in a vacuum, while the quantity of energy stored in an electric field per unit volume of a dielectric medium is greater. The capacitance of a capacitor filled with a dielectric is greater than it would be in a vacuum. The effects of the dielectric on electrical phenomena are described on a large, or macroscopic, scale by employing such*

⁴³ Remember, also, that the Law of Polarity (fire trigram) sits opposite the Law of Relativity (water trigram/Abyss).

*concepts as [dielectric constant](#), [permittivity](#), and electric polarization.*⁴⁴

*“In [electromagnetism](#), a **dielectric (or dielectric material or dielectric medium)** is an [electrical insulator](#) that can be [polarised](#) by an applied [electric field](#).*

When a dielectric material is placed in an electric field, [electric charges](#) do not flow through the material as they do in an [electrical conductor](#), because they have no loosely bound, or free, electrons that may drift through the material, but instead they shift, only slightly, from their average equilibrium positions, causing dielectric polarisation. Because of [dielectric polarisation](#), positive charges are displaced in the direction of the field and negative charges shift in the direction opposite to the field (for example, if the field is moving parallel to the positive x axis, the negative charges will shift in the negative x direction). This creates an internal electric field that reduces the overall field within the dielectric itself. If a dielectric is composed of weakly [bonded](#) molecules, those molecules not only become polarised, but also reorient so that their [symmetry axes](#) align to the field.⁴¹ The study of dielectric properties concerns storage and dissipation of electric and [magnetic energy](#) in materials.”⁴⁵ (sic, emphasis mine)

- c. In other words it’s an electric field, not dielectric; dielectric is a **property**. Electrification is the phenomenon. He is dead backwards here.
 - d. The loss of inertia comment makes me think that he means the dielectric property is removed as an object begins to move. An interesting hypothesis. Does he have data to test this idea?
 - e. The second sentence is a word salad for a hypothesis. In the end, a charge (electric field) solution to electrogravitics is far simpler, and geometrically already discussed in Bessel functions, which correlate with the Dougherty Set. Why reinvent the wheel the altstream has already painstakingly put together?
3. *“The 3-dimensional S-curve primordial force vector which extrapolates into as as the torus of what is called the magnetic field (=dielectric field in loss of inertia)”*
- a. Alright it seems here he has taken to refining the hypothesis using a geometric idea. It does remind me of the Dougherty Set. However, what does he mean by “S-curve” and “primordial force vector”? Is primordial fundamental? Is the force vector somehow more real than a magnetic line? Or is it a typical representation of the gradient of the magnetic field? Given his predilection for despising mainstream explanations, (claiming he is Steinmetzian, without citation of page number etc.), I somehow doubt that he would agree with the use of Gaussian curvature. But, I could be wrong. Why not say Gaussian curvature? This is what I could find about S-curvature:

“Abstract

In this paper, we give an explicit formula of the S-curvature of homogeneous Randers spaces and prove that a homogeneous Randers space with almost isotropic S-curvature must have vanishing S-curvature. As an application, we obtain a classification of homogeneous Randers space with almost isotropic

⁴⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/science/dielectric>

⁴⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dielectric>

*S-curvature in some special cases. Some examples are also given.*⁴⁶

Having a gander through the paper, I must say it is beyond me. If it is not beyond Ken, he needs to show me, because I don't remember this in our training at the University of Kentucky Electrical Engineering department. It certainly is mathematical just as General Relativity - which I know Ken despises⁴⁷ - and talks about Riemannian spaces. So the issue seems to me is that Ken still believes in space as an object. Wal Thornhill has [correctly] dealt with this delusion⁴⁸, as has Donald Scott⁴⁹, EE emeritus⁵⁰ and writer of the Birkeland Current paper⁵¹ which is currently state of the art about the subject. At any rate, space is not an object, that's the point of it. It is a mathematical and 'physical' reality of the ideal of a canvas. It doesn't 'exist' so much as it is named to describe the idea of the place where objects rest and move within. It's like naming 0, which isn't a number but a placeholder.

4. *"The dielectric is the hyperboloidal field of increasing inertia towards counterspace, both in discharge & manifestation."*

- a. Hyperboloid (figure at right): *"A hyperboloid is the surface obtained from a hyperboloid of revolution by deforming it by means of directional scalings, or more generally, of an affine transformation. A hyperboloid is a quadric surface, that is, a surface defined as the zero set of a polynomial of degree two in three variables."*

Figure 3 - Hyperboloid; credit: wiki

- b. If the dielectric property is caused by the increasing inertia - an idea I am not opposed to - towards counterspace, then the idea here is that the counterspace is 100% inertia. I have not seen this demonstrated anywhere, because the anti-space (philosophically thinking) is non physical. It interacts, mysteriously of course, with space via what has only been described as a "quantum foam". This foam has not been observed, and as I replied to Dartmouth College⁵² needs to be demonstrated before claiming it is fact. However, for the remainder of this paper,

⁴⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0926224508000648>

⁴⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_NQSv22TD2c, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2kkFnIB6jNI> etc.

⁴⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rZspAmawlpC>

⁴⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/thunderbolts-project/donald-scott>

⁵⁰ <https://www.amazon.com/Electric-Sky-Donald-Scott/dp/0977285111/>

⁵¹

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0ByRZ_FN_vit_bmtHMUUh2UE84YIU/view?resourcekey=0-cRIYhWTICbB4snbmBDF0fQ

⁵² https://www.academia.edu/63382042/ Something_from_Nothing_

as a test of internal consistency, I'm going to do Ken a favor and **assume the counterspace is physically real, and 100% inertia.**

- c. Both in discharge and manifestation, Ken seems to imply that manifestation comes about as a result of relief of charge. So the charge builds up, (potential) and then is *discharged* into a real S-curved space (according to Ken). This is a unique idea, I'll need to give it some thought. The present PEMC position is that of Quantum Chromodynamics⁵³, namely that the subatomic particles are energy-mass relations measured in charge (electronVolts), and then attain their form via accumulated superposition (so fast that it appears solid) throughout the various shaped clouds formed as the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle⁵⁴ dissolves away, revealing an exact position, but not a known vector. I admit this sounds ridiculous, so let me make a correction to it, and without the help of Randal space curvature!

Ramon's idea of matter

The charge potential of the particles is a placeholder for the collapsing of reality in the PPPC⁵⁵ into a known location where the positional relation of the particle to the other particles (at least one other) provides a field distortion of the counterspace. This field distortion itself is how the Aether attains its 'isness' and then this 'discharges' (fundamental electricity⁵⁶) from the counterspace the energy potential into the space (our Universal reality) to posit a 'real' not a 'virtual' particle. This real particle attains dimensional reality which could never, by definition of space, and therefore counterspace, have had dimension in potentiality, being **undifferentiated** and 'primordial'. This is the Hundun⁵⁷ of the Chinese sciences.

From there the field - i.e. relationship - expresses itself to one another, as a mesh network as it were, and they gain **relative** charge value, i.e. 'weight' or as he prefers, inertia.

If this is what Ken means, then he and I agree on the PEMC concept, and there is no disagreement there. Somehow I doubt it.

- d. As for the use of the hyperboloid this matches many known sets of PEMF manifestation, but not all of them. I think he is already contradicting himself unless he shows the transformations to go from toroidal to hyperboloidal. The need of some to make everything so simplex that my eyes want to bleed from the contradictions that follow is disturbing. It is a trend I see with Nassim Hamein and Leedskalnin, etc. and what I find interesting is how mal-adjusted many of these characters are. As I said before I don't know Ken personally, and he is known as the "angry photographer" but that doesn't mean he isn't well adjusted. His political and news awareness is good so he isn't a mentally ill, quack-attack

⁵³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/quantum/qcd>

⁵⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/science/uncertainty-principle>

⁵⁵ Potentiality-Possibility-Probability-Cloud

⁵⁶ Of which all the forms we know are 'sub-variants'

⁵⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hundun>

numerologist. But how he interfaces through his hyperboloidal chakra with the toroidal Krispy Kreme on Richmond Road is neither here nor there... what does matter is that his mind interfaces well with reality. (It seems to do fine, he owns land⁵⁸ and has a business⁵⁹ and clients)

Figure 4 - also a hyperboloid; credit: wiki
(they can also be triangular at the Z pinch)

As a cohort of alchemy, we are primarily interested in the MIMS⁶⁰ and mimsical application of natural philosophy to reality. Can Ken hang? I think he can. But I'd like to not see internal contradictions⁶¹.

Unless the paradox is invoked, in which case say it is invoked, do not pretend it is simple for the audience, it isn't. Compare the figures. Toroids and hyperboloids are not the same shape, though they can appear as a polar pair if the hyperbola matches the toroidal curvature. However, that leaves all the

rest of the counterspace. So if the torus is space (objectified), and the hyperboloid is counterspace, then what is counter to the counterspace (to define the entire infinite 3-D cube)? Houston, we have problems.

5. ***“Magnetism inversely is the toroidal field and force, i.e. energy dissipation. Together these are conjugate fields of the Universe and each field geometry is the inverse geometry of the other.”***
 - a. Sometimes, as I said, they are. But let's not limit him to boiled down mathematical boilerplate definitions. Let's take this as a conceptual-only definition. So the hyperboloid is 100% inertia and its energy is dissipated into the toroidal manifestation. A pretty idea, not altogether unlike my concept of Dual Direction Entropy⁶². Except... where and how does the field revert the energy back into inertia? Undefined.
Also, what of the counter-counterspace? This is the problem with objectifying space. The irony of this is that Ken appears to despise Einstein the man as well as the General Relativity cult and lies. But objectifying space-time is only a slice of difference from objectifying space itself. The Wu (void) is non-void in its potentiality, but void in form. Hence the Chinese said, “Real emptiness is not empty.”⁶³ Their depiction of it as a toroidal form is mental positration, but whose

⁵⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CwSLqotQDuQ>

⁵⁹ Although I cannot find it in the Registered Agent search
[https://web.sos.ky.gov/ftshow/\(S\(ht1h1jwz2znva5xm0prtoob\)\)/rasearch.aspx](https://web.sos.ky.gov/ftshow/(S(ht1h1jwz2znva5xm0prtoob))/rasearch.aspx)

⁶⁰ Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

⁶¹ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

⁶² Or Two Way Entropy “Cosmic Rearrangement” Ibid. pp. 2-3

⁶³ <https://terebess.hu/zen/xinming.html>

negentropation is the “black pearl hanging in the void of space.”⁶⁴ These are literal concepts of the Taoist alchemists, and not of the General Relativists, alone. Remember the Quantum folks focus on Earth trigram (Law of Vibration), the Relativists on River trigram (Law of Relativity), and the PEM people on Fire trigram (Law of Polarity). But all 8 trigrams are polar manifestations of the toroidal “ring” of the spheroidal taijitu, where the boundary circumference of the sphere is an empty, rotational, plasmoidal-torus alternating in binary values. (See, I can do it, too).

Figure 5 - Spheroidal Taijitu; credit: GrabCAD

- b. I don't agree that magnetism is all, nor that it is the only energy dissipation. If he isn't saying that, then why boil it down so hardcore? For a reminder, the Chinese scientists identified the properties (sublaws) of the Polarus:
 - i. Mutually Generating
 - ii. Mutually Consuming
 - iii. Mutually Opposing (dualism)
 - iv. Mutually Controlling
 - v. Mutually Dependent (codependent origination, Buddha)
 - vi. Infinitely Divisible
- c. These 6 sub-laws represent the reason for the Six Division existence:

i.	Taiyang	-	Lord	<i>L</i>	Fire/plasma
ii.	Yangming	-	Force	<i>F</i>	Wood/dendrite
iii.	Shaoyang	-	Aether	<i>A</i>	Water/Aether
iv.	Taiyin	-	Numbers	<i>N</i>	Metal/crystals
v.	Shaoyin	-	Physics/Principles (Laws)	<i>P</i>	Earth/solids
vi.	Jueyin	-	GOD /\	<i>G</i>	Wuji/Void
- d. This structure is spiral/chironal/helical, and so, as you can see, there are many geometries present, all controlled (of course) in the *N* power or domain.

⁶⁴ Liu Yiming, “Taoist I Ching” etc.

- e. The self-consistency of this MIMS diagram is already well established and retroactively peer-supported⁶⁵ by the ancient/archaic engineers, astrologers, and wu (shaman) of the most advanced (before ours) civilizations (Mayans, Egyptians, Suemrians, Zoroastrians, Chinese, Alegewi, etc.)
 - f. In summary, he isn't wrong outright, but he does not appear to be as fully correct as polar complete PEMC is.
6. *"Dielectricity (& Gravity): the dielectric is a dendritic discharge towards counterspace."*
- a. I suppose it is too much to ask for the definitions to start the document? I have already addressed (twice) how he is **wrong** about dielectrics, and if he thinks Steinmetz, Tesla, or Heaviside agree with him (or Dollard), he needs to provide a citation. The only citation on the document is "copyright Ken Wheeler."
 - b. The counterspace is pure inertia. (him)
 - c. It appears therefore that the dielectric (his) is some attempt of the real space to move dendritically towards the complete potential (is this how energy discharges back from the counterspace into space?).
 - d. It's a flowery idea, and vivid in imagery. But how realistic is this simplification? It seems to limit the means of energy dissipation, absorption, and resorption. I don't like these limits because they are monopolar, which is another way of saying non-existent. There are manifold means of energy dissipations:
 - i. Sound/Acoustic
 - ii. Light
 - iii. Wave
 - iv. Heat (special case)
 - v. More? (can we ever know the limits?)
 - e. He'd probably argue these are all the same method, if not apparent manifestation.
 - f. But that's the point of a fractal PEMC... the scale, zoom, and changes in gradient, curvatures, and all the circuit values will create factually different opportunities for interface. I prefer a more organic or cooking related image of the space/counterspace interaction. I prefer to use cake⁶⁶ (and eat it, too). It is all **overlaid one atop another, inseparable in the Life Aquatic**. They only appear differentiated, toroidal vs. hyperboloidal, etc. owing to the mortal-finitivity of the individual, the asymptote of this (Fibonacci), and the psychological 'bent' (and IQ) of the person in whom the impressed geometries are given, known, or even inherited. In the latter case the ancients and Rosicrucians⁶⁷ made reference to the stars controlling a life, and more modern, M. Clarage has postulated that the celestial bodies 'speak' to the minds⁶⁸ (transceiver Quantum brains?⁶⁹)

⁶⁵

http://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

⁶⁶ Try getting flour, milk, eggs, and sugar back out of the cake. You cannot. It has to be eaten and broken down with acids.

⁶⁷ https://www.rosicrucianfellowship.org/rays_archives/rays/burgoyne.pdf

⁶⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gRGzJg5A3m8>

⁶⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FbBA14Aydvw>

Electro-antenna DNA?⁷⁰) of the person. All the numerologists and geometers share the obsession of the unified mathematical vision, and yet come to different “it’s all so simple” conclusions! Why? Because they are on different floors of the same building, studying its architecture and shouting at one another on different floors. They see each other, as the building is made of glass. But darkly. And their projections are dimensional and self-limiting, whereas the Big G diagram⁷¹ does not mind the form it takes, although this one is supported by the pentacular form Jupiter’s South Pole has had (owing to Birkeland Currents connecting it to the sun). Note, though, the center (G) moved out to the outside, as it reconnected to Saturn⁷² (a Shamash remnant?) Therefore perhaps it is only the Jews who were right⁷³ (is this why their IQ is the highest, by far, on average?).

7. *“The smaller the space, the higher the dielectric, or capacitance. A spatial energy discharge (lightning, electrostatic). Capacitance discharge = increasing inertia. Inversely loss of said inertia = magnetism.”*

- a. Wow, there is a **lot** to unpack here, and to debunk. Firstly, capacitance is given by the following equation, which is not spatial (3D) but areal (2D):

$$C = \frac{\epsilon A}{d}$$

Where,

C = Capacitance in Farads

ϵ = Permittivity of dielectric (absolute, not relative)

A = Area of plate overlap in square meters

d = Distance between plates in meters

Figure 6 - Capacitance; equation (1)

- b. If he means to imply that the 3 dimensions are combinations of A and d, okay then do not treat it conceptually but literally. Because so far he has mostly spoken conceptually of toroidal and hyperboloidal (obviously we do not put donut shaped magnets on our fridge). So the main issue is actually that the **larger the Area and smaller the distance (gap)**, the higher the capacitance. That isn’t the same thing as saying smaller space. If I could create a massive plate separated by a small gap, as thin as is physically realistic, this would greatly increase the space and capacitance and lead to a discharge in AC conditions. That’s another thing, capacitance doesn’t matter in DC conditions. Is he ignoring half of reality?

⁷⁰ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21457072/>

⁷¹ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

⁷² November 2019, juno mission

⁷³ “Star of David”

- c. Since he brought up lightning and it is convenient, we shall use nature for this next debunk. Consider the following image:

Figure 7 - water spout (tornado/vortex) with lightning discharge; credit: Flickr

- i.* This is a cloud to 'ground' (water vapor to ocean) discharge. We can see this by the branch out
 - ii.* There is a possible leadin, or a camera artifact at the top
 - iii.* The dendritic feature is minimized as the current "pump n dump" is maximized in the plasma ion channel.
 - iv.* The proximity to the tornado, a vortical slow moving particle discharge upwards of **mostly cold, i.e. staticky air/vapor**, suggests a circuit of a dual layer nature.
 - v.* The capacitance of the large wall cloud plate and 'ground' is part and parcel of this AC circuit.
 - vi.* The tornadic (slow moving) is long discharge, the lightning (ionic) is short discharge... presumably to maintain the system, but potentially to alleviate it.
- d. So as we can easily see, there is a serious discharge and motion here, so in what way is there "increasing inertia"? There is certainly resistance to the motion, in the form of air friction and high pressure gradients. The Bernoulli Effect⁷⁴ also suggests that the fluids in motion are low pressure because the motion is

⁷⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bernoulli%27s_principle

alleviating inertia to the momentum of the system. So I am not sure if he means something different than he's saying, or just saying bunk?

- e. So it appears that if magnetism comes from the loss of counter spatial inertia, then the above weather system should have actually increased magnetic behavior (even without the lightning). Is this verifiable? Let's do a spot test...

okay found this interesting paper:

*"A SEARCH FOR RESIDUAL MAGNETISM ALONG A TORNADO PATH By Robert C. Costen and Clifford L. Fricke Langley Research Center SUMMARY A search for residual magnetism was made along the damage path of a strong tornado that passed through a residential section of Hazlehurst, Mississippi, on January 23, 1969. The search was made about 3 weeks after the storm. Over 3000 gauss-meter readings were taken on nailheads in 24 frame buildings at various points on both sides of the damage path, **but no evidence of residual magnetism attributable to the tornado was found.** However, measurements made near ground wires connected to the electric-meter boxes on two buildings indicated that transient currents of about 135 and 300 amperes had occurred in the wires. This finding suggests that residual-magnetism measurements on nails may be useful for detecting possible magnetic fields from ball lightning, damaging lightning strokes, or other sporadic electrical phenomena, since no prior instrumentation is required. A statistical analysis of the data from seven of the buildings showed that an axial dc electric current, if existent in the tornado, did not exceed 3900 amperes at touchdown near Fayette, Mississippi, and 6100 amperes during its most intense phase at Hazlehurst, Mississippi. These upper-bound values do not support the hydromagnetic vortex hypothesis, which requires 10⁶ to 10⁷ amperes and was suggested by Costen (Trans. Amer. Geophys. Union, vol. 49, Dec. 1968 and NASA TN D-5964) as possibly relevant to tornadoes. The data are inconclusive concerning the suggestion by Silberg (J. Atmos. Sci., vol. 23, Mar. 1966) that strong alternating electric currents may exist in tornadoes."⁷⁵ (emphasis added)*

- f. Remember the tornado is a discharge (slow as it is in electrical terms) of the capacitance in the system (and maintained through a form of cold air inductance). However, it does not appear to be particularly strengthened by a smaller space, per se, nor leave much magnetic residue. So I am not quite sure that Ken's ideas work in actuality.
8. "Gravity is mutual mass acceleration towards counterspace"
a. Where's the definition for mass? For acceleration?
9. "So-called gravity is non-discharging dielectric centripetal torsion dissipation (toroidal rarefaction, i.e. magnetism). Gravity is not a field modality unto itself, merely a dielectric sub-variant."
a. Holy word salad, Batman! In reverse he is redefining magnetism to be toroidal rarefaction, whatever that means, and therefore it is also the rest of that. I assure you this is not a simplification of the word gravity.
b. Fine, I agree Gravity is not a field unto itself: it is a charge matter.

⁷⁵ <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/19710027273/downloads/19710027273.pdf>

- i. *electric sub-variant; there, fixed it.
- c. Overall this entire paragraph is a meaningless concoction of \$10 words. Dielectric is non-conductive, therefore it doesn't discharge. The other half is apparently meaningless, in its ultimate result. We are describing why the celestial bodies stay near each other in space. Charge is the answer, not space-time, not dielectric fields, not strings, and not dark matter.

10. "Compound low-energy cyclic circuits"

- a. What the Heck is he trying to communicate here? This subtitle is out of control. All circuits, ultimately, are cycles.

11. "Coaxial energy circuit of the Aether-medium"

- a. So... Birkeland Currents⁷⁶?

Figure 8 - "Field-aligned Current", aka BC; a force-free model; credit: D. Scott⁷⁷

12. "Longitudinal rarefactions and

compressions of dielectric pulses, accompanied by transverse cycle magnetic & electric (magnetism & dielectricity) spatiotemporal manifestation."

- a. We're sort of repeating ourselves here, aren't we? Firstly, magnetism being separate from magnetic is kind of interesting, or is it this magical spread for the entirety?
- b. So what is diminution of density about longitudinal compressions? What is this meaningless concoction? As for dielectric pulses, he is really straining credulity: **it is electricity which pulses**, not the properties of the materials!
- c. "Transverse cycle" just means one wave; I believe he is basically referring to this:

Figure 9

- EM waves ([gif](#)); credit: wiki

- d. I mean, ultimately I already covered all of this in the Synopsis, but just basically, the above is a model, but the actual manifestation is probably coaxial, which I think he agrees.

⁷⁶ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2018/PP-53-01.PDF>

⁷⁷ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

13. *“The most efficient Aether modality of any field modality”*

- a. If he means the Birkeland Current is most efficient, this is correct. Isn't to do with transverse cycles but the geometries of the Bessel function.

Fig. 1: Current density and its two components. The magnitude of the total current density varies as $1/\sqrt{r}$.

$$j = \frac{C}{m^3} \frac{m}{s} = \frac{C/s}{m^2} = \frac{A}{m^2}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 10 - the efficiency of the Bessel function; credit: D. Scott⁷⁸

14. *“Light is not an emission, particle, wave-particle-duality, nor is light moving from A to B.”*

- a. While I agree with the middle portion he is again straining credulity. We do move light from A to B, and light comes from the Sun to Earth, from the Milky Way to the Sun, etc. It is emitted **from a source** and reflects *on a load*. He's being overly idealistic. I've covered the issue elsewhere, rote.

15. *“The rate of induction or hysteresis of the Aether is assumed ‘C’ or the speed of light.”*

- a. Agree.

16. *“This is the rate of saturation-propagation of the energy circuit of light.”*

- a. I mean... propagation implies movement, therefore contradicting point 14. Otherwise we agree, except there is no point in adding saturation. This isn't a chemical reaction. There is no saturation in Kirchhoff's Circuit Laws.

17. *“Tesla called light ‘a sound wave in the Aether,’ which is correct, sound is not an emission or something moving, rather it is a perturbation of the medium.”*

- a. We are playing some word games here. To perturb a medium, like water, something moves and strikes or goes through the water. It isn't, in this case a particle, to be sure. It is the circuit's rate of induction released via discharge. The RLC properties are carried via the Aether/medium (as a wave, modeled as a particle for convenience), from the Source (A) to the Load (B). If there is perfect reflection, no work is performed, which as Robitaille⁷⁹ has shown, undoes

⁷⁸ Ibid. pp. 2 (page 58 in journal)

⁷⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/robitaille>

Kirchhoff's Thermal Gas Laws and Planck.⁸⁰ In other words, they understood but not completely.

- b. As for Tesla, he too understood, but not completely⁸¹. Tis true he was a genius. Given today's data he'd far surpass anyone at the PEMC. But at the time he was making very educated speculations. We cannot utilize the Authority Fallacy here and presume upon his name alone. The fact is that he was an expert at telluric currents, AC current, transformation, resonance and electric field propagation, and the like. I have read Tesla, and he didn't talk about the dielectric field, but electromagnetism. He did not, however, know anything about plasma. He was obsolete by 1927 (the official naming of plasma). If he had embraced Birkeland, Langmuir, and TT Brown, he'd have accomplished far more, than speculating about light being a sound wave. Even if it were, that doesn't help one much in harnessing its power. However, the ancient Egyptians, which Birkeland (and later C. Dunn) well knew, used acoustics to make MASER Hydrogen power, and attract electricity from the Van Allen belts, and propagate **electric fields** to power their Dendera bulbs⁸² and power tools, etc.

12.4 Birkeland's Terrella Experiments

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Fig. 12.12 Birkeland's 8-cm globe. (Left): Experiment parameters adjusted such that the inflow-outflow currents are visible. (Right): Experiment parameters adjusted such that the ground or atmospheric currents are mostly visible

Figure 11 - Birkeland's ingenious experiments which eluded Tesla; credit: Dr. A. Peratt⁸³

18. "THE AETHER: *Inertia 'in' counterspace. All fields are Aether perturbation modalities.*"
- a. Why does he put in in single quotes? If counterspace is objectified, because space is objectified, then absolutely inertia could be inside it. So he has a working hypothesis here about the Aether, that it is inertia, or resistance to motion, in the counterspace. That's a flowery definition, and I personally think

⁸⁰ <https://vixra.org/pdf/1502.0007v2.pdf>

⁸¹ <http://edisontechcenter.org/tesladebunked.html>

⁸² <https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-technology/dendera-light-0081>

⁸³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/peratt>

nowhere as useful as my own, nor supported by the experimental High-Energy Physics. I'd like to see his *data* and compare it to QED/QCD.

- b. I don't necessarily disagree with the second sentence, except I'd like to know what he means by modalities. Delivery methods ... of energy? Seems agreeable and self-evident. How else would it be unified if not for this?

19. "Pure non-Cartesian potential."

- a. And... right away we're smack into my problem with his work. His book⁸⁴ is nearly unreadable, due to the visible obstruction of it. Nevertheless, the main issue isn't visual but the propensity to suddenly, completely turn on a dime into undefined territory that goes nowhere. Potential is **well** defined, and it is non-geometric:

"electric potential, the amount of [work](#) needed to move a unit charge from a reference point to a specific point against an [electric field](#). Typically, the reference point is [Earth](#), although any point beyond the influence of the electric field charge can be used."⁸⁵

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$$V = k \frac{Q}{r} (2)$$

Figure 12 previous: Cavendish's diagram of electric potential. It can be measured in any geometric coordinate system. Cartesian has nothing specific to do with it; although the Cartesian dimension of distance is the easiest way to divide the charge (Q). But it could be spherical or cylindrical coordinates, etc.

I want to also address this idea that potential could be dielectric. Where is this idea coming from? It only could make sense, if at all, from its relationship to the electric potential! And that is related, of course, to charge! If Ken was right and the electronics and electrical engineers **worldwide** were wrong, then touchscreens couldn't work. Literally they work upon the increase of point charges, not upon magnetics or resistance. There is a change in potential itself, and this induces a change in the circuit. The electric force is useful, and it is **not** a dielectric force-field. That is wordplay.

I'd like anyone that doubts me - for Ken is fantastically confident in his sophistry here - to consult not me, and not modern science but the Hawkin's Electrical Guides⁸⁶ of the 1920s. They are richly worded and drawn, and incredibly lucid. I'll drop some samples from volume 1 (which I bought on ebay) here:

⁸⁴ <https://ia802209.us.archive.org/32/items/magnetism1small/magnetism1small.pdf>

⁸⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/science/electric-potential>

⁸⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/hawkins-field-guides>

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CHAPTER I

ELECTRICITY

Nature and Source of Electricity.—What is electricity? This is a question that is frequently asked, but has not yet been satisfactorily answered. It is a force, subject to control under well known laws.

While the nature and source of electricity still remain a mystery, many things about it have become known, thus, it is positively assured that electricity never manifests itself except when there is some mechanical disturbance in ordinary matter.

The true nature of electricity has not yet been discovered. Many think it a quality inherent in nearly all the substances, and accompanied by a peculiar movement or arrangement of the molecules. Some assume that the phenomena of electricity are due to a peculiar state of strain or tension in the ether which is present everywhere, even in and between the atoms of the most solid bodies. If the latter theory be the true one, and if the atmosphere of the earth be surrounded by the same ether, it may be possible to establish these assumptions as facts.

The most modern supposition regarding this matter, by Maxwell, is that light itself is founded on electricity, and that *light waves* are merely *electro-magnetic waves*. The theory "tha

electricity is related to, or identical with, the luminiferous ether," has been accepted by the most prominent scientists.

But while electricity is still a mystery, much is known about the laws governing its phenomena. Man has mastered this mighty force and made it his powerful servant; he can produce it and use it.

Electricity, it is also conceded, is without weight, and, while it is without doubt, one and the same, it is for convenience sometimes classified according to its motion, as:

1. Static electricity, or electricity *at rest*;
2. Current electricity, or electricity *in motion*;
3. Magnetism, or electricity *in rotation*;
4. Electricity *in vibration* (radiation).

Other useful divisions are:

1. Positive;
2. Negative electricity;
3. Static;
4. Dynamic electricity.

Static Electricity.—This is a term employed to define electricity produced by friction. It is properly employed in the sense of a static charge which shows itself by the attraction or repulsion between charged bodies.

When static electricity is discharged, it causes more or less of a current, which shows itself by the passage of sparks or a brush discharge; by a peculiar prickling sensation; by a peculiar smell due to its chemical effects; by heating the air or other substances in its path; and sometimes in other ways.

Current Electricity.—This may be defined as the quantity of electricity which passes through a conductor in a given time—or, electricity in the act of being discharged, or electricity in motion.

An electric current manifests itself by heating the wire or conductor; by causing a magnetic field around the conductor and by causing chemical changes in a liquid through which it may pass.

Dynamic Electricity.—This term is used to define current electricity to distinguish it from static electricity.

Radiated Electricity.—Electricity in vibration. Where the current oscillates or vibrates back and forth with extreme rapidity, it takes the form of waves which are similar to waves of light.

Positive electricity.—This term expresses the condition of the point of an electrified body having the higher energy from which it flows to a lower level. The sign which denotes this phase of electric excitement is +; all electricity is either positive or negative.

Negative Electricity.—This is the reverse condition to the above and is expressed by the sign or symbol—. These two terms are used in the same sense as *hot* and *cold*.

NOTE.—In 1749, Benjamin Franklin, observing lightning to possess almost all the properties observable in electric sparks, suggested that the electric action of points, which was discovered by him, might be tried on thunderclouds, and so draw from them a charge of electricity. He proposed, therefore, to fix a pointed iron rod to a high tower, but shortly after succeeded in another way. He sent up a kite during the passing of a storm, and found the wetted string to conduct the electricity to the earth, and to yield abundance of sparks. These he drew from a key tied to the string, a silk ribbon being interposed between his hand and the key for safety. Leyden jars could be charged, and all other electrical effects produced, by the sparks furnished from the clouds. The proof of the identity was complete. The kite experiment was repeated by Romas, who drew from a metallic string sparks 9 feet long. In 1753, Richmann, of St. Petersburg, who was experimenting with a similar apparatus, was struck by a sudden discharge and killed.

Atmospheric Electricity is the free electricity of the air which is almost always present in the atmosphere. Its exact cause is unknown.

The phenomena of atmospheric electricity are of two kinds; there are the well known manifestations of thunderstorms; and there are the phenomena of continual slight electrification in the air, best observed when the weather is fine; the Aurora constitutes a third branch of the subject.

Fig. 1.—The electric eel. There are several species inhabiting the water, and which have the power of producing electric discharges by certain portions of their organism. The best known of these are the *Torpedo*, the *Gymnotus*, and the *Silurus*, found in the Nile and the Tiger. The Electric Ray, of which there are three species inhabiting the Mediterranean and Atlantic is provided with an electric organ on the back of its head, as shown in the illustration. This organ consists of laminae composed of polygonal cells to the number of 800 or 1000, or more, supplied with four large bundles of nerve fibres; the under surface of the fish is -, the upper +. In the Surinam eel, the electric organ goes the whole length of the body along both sides. It is able to give a very severe shock, and is a formidable antagonist when it has attained its full length of 5 or 6 feet.

Frictional Electricity is that produced by the friction of one substance against another.

Resinous Electricity.—The kind of electricity produced upon a resinous substances such as sealing wax, resin, shellac, rubber or amber when rubbed with wool or fur. Resinous electricity is *negative electricity*.

Vitreous Electricity.—A term applied to the positive electricity developed in a glass rod by rubbing it with silk. This electric charge will attract to itself bits of pith or paper which have been repelled from a rod of sealing wax or other resinous substance which had been rubbed with wool or fur.

CHAPTER IX

MAGNETISM

Magnetism.—The ancients applied the word “magnet,” *magnes lapes*, to certain hard black stones which possess the property of attracting small pieces of iron, and as discovered later, to have the still more remarkable property of pointing

FIG. 93. — Simple compass. It consists of a magnetic needle resting on a steel pivot, protected by a brass case covered with glass, and a graduated circle marked with the letters N, E, S, W, to indicate the cardinal points; *a b* is a lever which arrests the needle by pushing it against the glass when the button *d* is pressed.

north and south when hung up by a string. At this time the magnet received the name of *lodestone* or “leading stone.” It is commonly, though incorrectly, spelled loadstone.

Ques. Describe two kinds of magnetism.

Ans. Magnets have two opposite kinds of magnetism or magnetic poles, which attract or repel each other in much the same way as would two opposite kinds of electrification.

Magnetic Field.—When a straight bar magnet is held under a piece of card board upon which iron filings are sprinkled, the filings will arrange themselves in curved lines radiating from the poles. If a horse shoe magnet be held at right angles to the plane of the card board, the filings will arrange themselves in curved lines, as shown in fig. 108. These lines are called *magnetic lines of force* or simply *lines of force*; they show that the medium surrounding a magnet is in a state of stress, the space so affected being called the *magnetic field*.

FIG. 100.—Badly magnetized bar. Properly magnetized magnets have only two poles; it is possible, however, by special or careless magnetization, to produce magnets with more than two poles, but no process will produce a magnet with a single pole. If an abnormal magnet with more than two poles be dipped into iron filings, the latter will adhere at places other than the two ends, as shown in the illustration. The polarities are alternately N and S; that is, the regions N, B, N, have north polarity, while A and C have south polarity. These are known as *consequent poles*.

FIGS. 101 to 107.—Effect of breaking a magnet into several parts. If a magnetized needle be broken, each part will be found to be a complete magnet having a N and S pole. The sub-division may be continued indefinitely, but always with the same result as indicated in the figure. This is evidence of the correctness of the molecular theory of magnetism, which states that *the molecules of a magnet are themselves minute magnets arranged in rows with their opposite poles in contact*.

Ques. What is the extent and character of the magnetic field?

Ans. The influence of a magnet is supposed to extend in all directions indefinitely, however, the effect is very slight beyond a comparatively limited area.

Magnetic Force.—This is the force with which a magnet attracts or repels another magnet or any piece of iron or steel. The force varies with the distance, being greater when the magnet is nearer and less when the magnet is farther off. The following are the laws relating to magnetic force:

1. *Like magnetic poles repel one another; unlike magnetic poles attract one another.*
2. *The force exerted between two magnetic poles varies inversely as the square of the distance between them.*

Magnetic Circuit.—The path taken by magnetic lines of force is called a magnetic circuit; the greater part of such a circuit is usually in magnetic material, but there are often one or more air gaps included. The total number of lines of force in the circuit is known as the *magnetic flux*.

Ques. How is magnetic flux measured?

Ans. By a unit called the maxwell.

Named after James Clerk Maxwell the Scottish physicist.

Ques. What is the maxwell?

Ans. *The amount of magnetism passing through every square centimetre of a field of unit density.*

Ques. What is the unit of field strength?

Ans. The gauss.

Ques. What is a gauss?

Ans. *The intensity of field which acts on a unit pole with a force of one dyne. It is equal to one line of force per square*

centimetre. Named after Karl Friedrich Gauss, the German mathematician.

The Magnetic Effect of the Current.—Hans Christian Oersted, the Danish scientist, discovered in 1819 that a magnetic needle tends to set itself at right angles to a wire carrying an electric current. He also found that the way in which the needle turns, whether to the right or left of its usual position, depends, 1, upon the position of the wire that carries the current, when

FIG. 112.—Illustrating Maxwell's "corkscrew rule" for relative directions of current and lines of force. According to the rule: *the direction of the current and that of the resulting magnetic force are in the same relation to each other as is the forward travel and rotation of an ordinary corkscrew.* Thus, in the figure, if a current flow through the wire *ab* in the direction from *a* to *b*, the magnetic lines will encircle the wire in the direction of the arrow *ro* which shows the direction in which the corkscrew must be turned to advance in the direction of the arrow *n*.

it be above or below the needle, and 2, on the direction in which the current flows through the wire.

To keep these movements in mind numerous rules have been suggested, of which the following will be found convenient:

Corkscrew Rule.—*If the direction of travel of a right handed corkscrew represent the direction of the current in a straight conductor, the direction of rotation of the corkscrew will represent the direction of the magnetic lines of force.*

FIG. 113.—Experiment showing direction of lines of force in the magnetic field surrounding a conductor carrying an electric current. A piece of copper wire is pierced through the center of a sheet of cardboard, and carried vertically for two or three feet then bent around to the terminals of a battery or other source of current. If iron filings be sprinkled over the card while the current is passing, they will arrange themselves in circles around the wire, thus indicating the form of the magnetic field surrounding the conductor. Compass needles may also be used to show the direction of the lines of force at any point.

FIG. 114.—Right hand rule to determine the direction of magnetic field around a conductor carrying a current. The thumb of the right hand is placed along the conductor, pointing in the direction in which the current is flowing, then, if the fingers be partly closed, as shown in the illustration, the finger tips will point in the direction of the magnetic whirls.

Hysteresis.—The term hysteresis has been given by Ewing to the subject of *lag of magnetic effects behind their causes*. Hysteresis means to “lag behind,” hence its application to denote the *lagging of magnetism, in a magnetic metal, behind the magnetizing flux which produces it.*

Ques. What is the cause of hysteresis?

Ans. It is due to the friction between the molecules of iron or other magnetic substance which requires an expenditure of energy to change their positions.

Figs. 124 and 125.—Experiment illustrating the molecular theory of magnetism. Coarse steel filings are placed inside a small glass tube and the contents magnetized. It will be found that filings which at first had no definite arrangement will rearrange themselves under the influence of magnetic force, and assume symmetrical positions, each one lying in line with, or parallel to its neighbor, as shown in the lower figure.

Ques. When do the molecules change their positions?

Ans. Both in the process of magnetization and demagnetization.

Ques. What becomes of the loss of energy due to hysteresis?

Ans. It is converted into heat in changing the positions of the molecules during magnetization and demagnetization.

Ewing gives the value for the energy in ergs dissipated per cubic centimetre, for a complete cycle of doubly reversed strong magnetization for a number of substances as follows:

20. "Electricity. The two components of the electric field are the magnetic & the dielectric"

- a. I can only presume, and maybe he can correct me if this is wrong, but this idea is a Dollardesque^{87 88} sentiment, born of the following equations:

<p>MAGNETIC PROPORTION</p> $\alpha_m = \sqrt{LM}$ <p>NUMERIC</p>	<p>DIELECTRIC PROPORTION</p> $\alpha_d = \sqrt{CK}$ <p>NUMERIC</p>
<p>NATURAL INDUCTANCE</p> $L_s = \sqrt{\frac{L}{M}}$ <p>HENRY</p>	<p>NATURAL CAPACITANCE</p> $C_s = \sqrt{\frac{C}{K}}$ <p>FARAD</p>

Figure 25 - Four Quadrant (Dollard) System, aka Quadrapolar Resonance; credit: Dollard/Steinmetz⁸⁹

Figure 26 - "Galactic Life in a light bulb?
 Cosmic forms appear in plasma discharges
 inside glass bulb. Created by Eric Dollard at the
 old BSRF Laboratories, Santa Barbara,
 California, 1988."; credit: Dollard; see.. Even
 Dollard himself learned plasma is an inherent
 discussion, even if he wasn't familiar with the
 subject and mistook it.

- b. It is also in Dollard's work⁹⁰ these following quotes:

"Capacitance

The phenomena of capacitance is a type of electrical energy storage in the form of a field in an enclosed space. This space is typically bounded by two parallel metallic plates or two metallic foils on an intervening insulator or dielectric. A nearly infinite variety of more complex structures can exhibit

⁸⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/dollard>

⁸⁸ https://ericpdollard.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/theory_of_wireless_power_eric_dollard.pdf

⁸⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/steinmetz>

⁹⁰ <https://ericpdollard.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/dielectricity-and-capacitance-by-eric-dollard.pdf>

capacity, as long as a difference in electric potential exists between various areas of the structure. The oscillating coil represents one possibility as to a capacitor of more complex form, and will be presented here.

Capacitance Inadequately Explained

*The perception of capacitance as used today is wholly inadequate for the proper understanding of this effect. Steinmetz mentions this in his introductory book *Electric Discharges, Waves and Impulses*. To quote, "Unfortunately, to large extent in dealing with dielectric fields the prehistoric conception of the electrostatic charge (electron) on the conductor still exists, and by its use destroys the analogy between the two components of the electric field, the magnetic and the dielectric, and makes the consideration of dielectric fields unnecessarily complicated.*

Lines of Force as Representation of Dielectricity

*Steinmetz continues, "There is obviously no more sense in thinking of the capacity current as current which charges the conductor with a quantity of electricity, than there is of speaking of the inductance voltage as charging the conductor with a quantity of magnetism. But the latter conception, together with the notion of a quantity of magnetism, etc., has vanished since Faraday's representation of the magnetic field by lines of force." *The Laws of Lines of Force* All the lines of magnetic force are closed upon themselves, all dielectric lines of force terminate on conductors, but may form closed loops in electromagnetic radiation. These represent the basic laws of lines of force. It can be seen from these laws that any line of force cannot just end in space"*

"Dielectric Energy Storage Spatially Different than Magnetic Energy Storage

Unlike magnetism the energy is forced or compressed inwards rather than outwards. Dielectric lines of force push inward into internal space and along axis, rather than pushed outward broadside to axis as in the magnetic field. Because the lines are mutually repellent certain amounts of broadside or transverse motion can be expected but the phenomena is basically longitudinal. This gives rise to an interesting paradox that will be noticed with capacity. This is that the smaller the space bounded by the conducting structure the more energy that can be stored. This is the exact opposite of magnetism. With magnetism, the units volumes of energy can be thought of as working in parallel but the unit volumes of energy in association with dielectricity can be thought of as working in series.
<http://ericpdollard.com> <http://energyscienceconference.com>

Voltage is to Dielectricity as Current is to Magnetism

With inductance the reaction to change of field is the production of voltage. The current is proportionate to the field strength only and not velocity of field. With capacity the field is produced not by current but voltage. This voltage must be accompanied by current in order for power to exist. The reaction of capacitance to change of applied force is the production of current. The current is directly proportional to the velocity of field strength. When voltage increases a reaction current flows into capacitance and thereby energy accumulates. If voltage does

not change no current flows and the capacitance stores the energy which produced the field. If the voltage decreases then the reaction current reverses and energy flows out of the dielectric field. As the voltage is withdrawn the compression within the bounded space is relieved. When the energy is fully dissipated the lines of force vanish.”

- c. I'm not writing a reply to Dollard, but to Wheeler. However, let me just say that Dollard is very lucid here. Steinmetz easily discusses his idea of the dielectric field and represents the problem as owing to the particle-obsession of the ages, and not owing to a problem with the electromagnetic theory itself. In essence, the *phenomenon of electricity* is a polar reaction of the magnetic (attraction-repulsion pulsation) and the conductor's dielectric properties, which are field-connected from the source to load. Note the continual polar relationships forming which construct the electric phenomenon. That does not disquiet or destroy the actual electric force effect. It is still quite real.
 - d. Note the final paragraph I have quoted of Dollard. Potential (voltage) comes from the change to the field - very Chinese - and he succinctly and correctly explains the capacitance mechanism.
21. *“Electricity is a compound cyclic field modality composed of both components of the primordial conjugate fields.”*
- a. Look, I too am an alchemist. Not the Pb into Au kind, but the transmutation of material reality through breath and bioelectric and spiritual work kind⁹¹.

official-kircheis

The first thing you discover when using the philosophers stone is that since Pb weighs 202 g/mol and Au 197 g/mol, every mole transmuted causes a 107 kiloton TNT explosion. You will not make a second discovery, for obvious reasons.

Figure 27 - a little humor by “official-kircheis”

This wording is referring back to the primordial conjugate fields, while he constantly decries that no one knows what a field is. It's problematic. It's not really wrong, in that electricity creates a situation between the physical reality and the magnetic reality. That physical reality is both dielectric and conductive, and in inverse proportions. The more dielectric the less conductive, and vice versa. The discharge phenomenon is *sometimes* dendritic, but not only. At any rate, it is best typified in plasma, but not only in plasma. However my main issue is only in the

⁹¹ https://www.academia.edu/49945612/Alchemical_Process

complexification of the matter's conceptualization, not necessarily in the description. Again, compare to Hawkins or Dollard⁹², etc.

22. *“Understanding electromagnetism and all electrical phenomena becomes abundantly simplex when one grasps that the electric field is a compounded binary field of magnetic & dielectric fields. Electrical transmission requires conductor field-guides for its directed propagation.”*

- a. The binary field is more abstruse than that, for the Yin and Yang are the primary fields he has mentioned, and electricity and magnetism are merely aspects of “rarefaction” under this binary. If one were to analogize Yin as “Earth” and Yang as “Heaven”, one can extrapolate much about Heaven and Earth, and yet not be discussing the Yin and Yang primordial fields. Similarly, when one speaks of the dielectric|electric polar relationship (Yang) and of diamagnetic|magnetic polar relationship (Yin) as a formed pair is to acknowledge the extreme disparity of the two *in relation to each other*, not within themselves, which is obvious. Flow, don't flow, attract, don't attract... this is non-contentious and self-evident. There is no difficulty in electrical engineering currently for him to correct. The electric field is something you can measure without worrying about the magnetic field on account of the same reason one can consider a man or Yang itself and not necessarily consider a woman or Yin while in the closed thought or system. We do it all the time, and the behavior of men and of women is known to change depending upon the removal or placement of a member of the opposite sex in the group. Granted, within men and women there is yin and yang both, and in relation to each man, some are more masculine and some more feminine. But once a yin pole (female) is added to the group the dynamic becomes obvious (and children reflect this in their psychological relationship to criticism and discipline); and vice versa. So there is no disagreement here with Ken and myself, so long as he doesn't make a big deal out of re-re-re-re-discovering that which has been known all along. Wheel is round, water is wet, Earth is globe, Sun is hot, Red is bright, Blue is beautiful, etc. Nothing intriguing in and of itself. Now, you commingle the poles, and then the fun begins!

23. *“Light being more compounded has its own field guides in the nature of its coaxial circuit.”*

- a. Again he hasn't defined compounded, but it appears to be an alchemical materia-media treatment of the ‘substance’ of light, which, as I stated before (and he agreed, though he contradicts himself in video) is **not a particle**. As for ownership of the field guides, not sure that is pertinent, but it is the *P* domain or power that owns them, not light. The relationship of *P* and *A* domains is that *P* contains the *A* power, as Earth contains Water. That isn't a mere controlling, it is a relationship (grandmother-grandson), mediated by the *N* domain (Metal/mother). This relationship is anciently discussed in the (Huangdi) Neijing

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https://www.academia.edu/4388573/Symbolic_Representation_of_the_Generalized_Electric_Wave_Eric_Dollard_New_and_Remade
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cCJcU7INwnU> & <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TttHkDRuyZw>

Suwen⁹³, if Ken would like a reference. The relationship keeps the circuit (of family) flowing, and in the case of It All, the family never breaks down. What an ideal for society!

b. Agree on coaxial nature. Glad to see he knows D. Scott is correct.

24. *“Electricity is not a field modality unto itself ... ”*

a. I’m not aware of a single person who said the phenomenon of electricity is ‘unto itself’. Thornhill has suggested the electric is primary, and others disagree. I have said that argument is pointless because it is a phase relationship issue, but obviously the Chinese are most correct: Yang leads the Yin, Yin restrains and generates the Yang. Therefore electricity leads, magnetism controls the plasma, plasma generates the electricity; and Electricity dominates (taiyang) the entire PEM relationship. That’s what we see in Electric Stars⁹⁴, and in human relationships, and biological systems. It is so self-evident, I don’t need to cite a single thing about it.

25. **“SIMPLEX ULTRA-HIGH ENERGY CIRCUITS:**

Matter: Ultra-high-energy light. No frequency. When frequency & energy are so high, light reaches a non-propagating energy-barrier.”

a. And... we’re off the rails again.

i. Ambiguous. GA, TA, PA... GHz, THz, PHz... all of these pale compared to infinity. It’s arbitrarily in meaning to the human scale only, unless one considers the repetition (but spiraled and chaotically rearranged) of the fractal nature of the Universe. Real gods... not the petty planets and stars.

ii. Wrong, definitely there is frequency. The Law of Vibration doesn’t stop for Mr. Wheeler.

iii. I hope he intends to either explain the case he is thinking of, or show this.

26. *“There is only one fundamental particle with two expressed modalities. All free neutrons become protons. This is well established fact.”*

a. I mean, it is a fact that neutrons are electron-positron pairs, but so what? The electron’s reification is pure energy (i.e. the model called a photon), and proton’s reification is the positron. That is their “fundamental” or “essential” or “primordial” nature, meaning their most basic physical foundation, if there is one at all.

b. The proton is misnamed, as it is actually the Yin (in the same way an egg is huge and a sperm small and insignificant, because the egg contains the energy storage). Franklin got the positive/negative designations backwards, and usually EE’s ignore the issue or flip it.

c. Nevertheless, actually the electron has a yin aspect as well as the yang. It might be small, but there is a magnetic dipole to the electron as sure as there is night to day.

“The electron magnetic dipole moment is called g/2 when it is measured in Bohr magnetons. It is one of the most accurately measured properties of an

⁹³ https://www.academia.edu/43951590/Huang_Di_Nei_Jing_Su_Wen

⁹⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Electric-Sky-Donald-Scott/dp/0977285111>

*elementary particle, and one of the properties of a particle that can be most accurately predicted by the standard model of particle physics.*⁹⁵

27. *“The so-called electron-particle does not exist, rather is one unit of dielectric induction.”*

- a. Good luck with that in explaining the Scanning Electron Microscope, or single point charges in the oil drop experiments, without it. I'd rather say we do not know what its essential Yang nature is, being that oneness is invisible. However, one unit of dielectric induction sure is a long way to say electron. It's word games, Mr. Wheeler. You mean to say there is no billiard ball of electric charge, but actually they can impart momentum⁹⁶ because it has mass. Mass is charge, and round and round we go. Don't make this more difficult than it has to be.

28. *“All atoms are compounded modalities of hydrogen.”*

- a. Structured Atomic Model (SAM)⁹⁷ is beyond this paper, but needless to say, he means protons.

29. *“Only one mass-particle exists, which is trans-spectral ultra-high energy light.”*

- a. Point 14, light is not a particle, and never is or was. This is (western) alchemical bunk. Religion in science.
- b. Also there is clearly more, or else explain It All.

30. *“When an ultra-high energy threshold is reached, frequency becomes impossible.”*

- a. Wrong, on so many levels.
- b. Practicably, in engineering we would see this, but that's not relevant to the bare cosmological facts. It is all relative!

31. *“This is the tension-barrier of the Aether itself & the junction at which matter is manifest.”*

- a. Flowery, and wrong. He is wanting to define, by himself, the Isness of atoms and protons. But the fact is that light circuits are highly unstable and temporary, and solids and molecules are not, on the whole, particularly temporary that we can see. Some portions of the molecule and nucleus, maybe even neutrons break down into radiant energy, but that must be resorbed by the spongy counterspace (SCS) itself. The fact remains, though, that there is a strong relationship of stability between existence and light. That does not mean that a proton, for example, is perfectly trapped light at an ultra-high energy threshold. We can measure light from a source in lumens and determine its energy. At a **relatively low threshold** it becomes very hot and dangerous. Never, however, has anyone spontaneously burst into flames from consuming an apple. Let's be real... most atomic energy in our daily lives and world exists at a lower energy threshold, all

⁹⁵ <https://cfp.physics.northwestern.edu/gabrielse-group/electron-magnetic-moment.html>

⁹⁶ <https://opentextbc.ca/universityphysicsv2openstax/chapter/momentum-and-radiation-pressure/>

⁹⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models/sam>

things atomic being equal fission-wise. There is, however, a tremendous amount of energy bound up in the internal fields of the atom's particle relationships.

- b. What in the heck is a tension-barrier? Define, please.
32. "SCALAR: *Trans-luminal sub-matter. Measure in volts per seconds. No transverse component, longitudinal torsion-energy.*"
 - a. If Mr. Wheeler needs a word salad machine there is a random word generator on the internet. <https://randomwordgenerator.com/>
 - b. It seems we've entered over-time here and this is 'special cases.' I'd like to request one for superconductivity, Vander Waals forces, piezoelectricity, cavitation, etc. Why stop at scalar behaviors?
33. "Magnetic force-torsion 'bubbles' tapping inertia-release from the Aether."
 - a. What is anyone supposed to do with this sentence?
34. "The higher the energy of scalar the lower the frequency, inverse to that of light."
 - a. So theoretically at 0 frequency we have infinite scalar wave behavior? So DC current is scalar? Someone tell that to my AA's. Needless to say I don't think he has a single shred of proof of this.
35. "Powerful & destructive energy-dissipation force-cavitation of the Aether"
 - a. There it is! Cavitation. Not defined or explained... but by and by the simplex will just become complex because of the fractal nature of It All.
 - b. Again, what is anyone to do with this sentence? It has no particular place in the discussion, and just seems to be a randomly cavitating thought in his head, undeveloped and raw.
36. "BLACK HOLE: *Ultra-high energy super-mass with no magnitude.*"
 - a. Well there is a magnitude, we have measurements. They are **not** infinite. That's all Einstein's bunk turned into more bunk. There is, by best estimation, $\sim 10^{18}$ A, or a billion billion amperes exiting from a typical Active Galactic Nuclei⁹⁸.
 - b. Again, no definition of mass, and ambiguity on ultra-high. Sure, relative to humans, yes. But perhaps not to God?
37. "Dielectric acceleration has overthrown magnetism's ability to keep this super-mass in the mass-visible universe."
 - a. What a load of toss! Firstly, magnetic pinches are always invisible to the naked eye, and these AGN are no exception.
 - b. But we "see" almost everything coming out of them, as there is a sudden compression upon the Aether until it pulls pure negentropy (ORDER) out of the SCS and into our visible Universe. It is entirely mass-visible, as mass is charge related and there *is* an inertial weight to these AGN! Obviously it is quite huge in stellar terms.
 - c. Also, what is the acceleration to do with it? Physical/velocity? Frequency approaching infinite? In reality these are in the THz range, and therefore nowhere near infinite. Still, they are unbelievable in power. Imagine what God's perspective in the fractal would be!
38. "Black Holes emit at their gyro-magnetic precessional axis, ultra-high energy light, i.e. hydrogen."

⁹⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

- a. No comment. More than that.
39. *“These are called galactic jets.”*
- a. Lamentably so. They are Birkeland Currents. Is there no respect anywhere?
40. *“A black hole is simple, is an Aether-torsion ‘faucet’ emitting enormous amounts of hydrogen, or U.H.F. light”*
- a. Where to begin? Well, at the end of all of this, he shows his ceiling by resorting to the Magnetohydrodynamic farce of using water⁹⁹ as an analogy of plasma. Plasma is not a gas or a liquid, it is plasma. Aether is being ejected, not emitted¹⁰⁰, from AGN for a specific reason. The GR theorists want it to be a “white hole” “tear” in space-time (their Aether) releasing contents. This is all rubbish, of course, because the same effect can be had in a lab, and no extra matter has been added at all, just ‘ultra high’ (relative to humans) magnetism. They will do this experiment in various ways, and it’ll be the same result. Plasmoids implode at most settings, but once we have the right settings they will eject energy from the Aether (which got it from counterspace) at present thinking of a 7:100 ratio. SAFIRE got 100% temperature expulsion for 7% power input in dark mode of plasma.¹⁰¹
- b. Hydrogen is not light anymore than anything else is or isn’t.

Stray Video Comments

This wouldn’t be a response without the general PEMC response to some of the offhand, but oft-repeated (by himself) comments that accompany his videos, and respectfully I think they are worthy of inclusion here. It is respectful because he attempts to clarify himself, and also that way nothing is in isolation, and he is considered in context within his own paradigm, and not only in duality versus EPEMC, Electric Universe, Standard Model, Dollardism, etc.

- *“Simplicity is divinity”* .. then keep it simpler, Ken; PEM is huge and expansive, but simplex. Re-inventing EM engineering and electronics history is not. We have enough to deal with: these fake “Dark Universe”: GR and Big Bang and Black Hole nonsensicalists without having a schizophrenic identity crisis and breakdown.
- *“Ultimately there is only one category... the Aether.”* No. The Taiyi is Wuji, Dao, Di (God), and Aether/Heaven is downstream of these. $0+1=1$; that one is God/It All, and Heaven is only found in relation to creation itself.
- *“People talk about fields in the Aether, as if there is something in the Aether.”* Yes... us, and the planet. Don’t make this harder than it is. We do the vertical interferometer experiments¹⁰² and we see the Aether is thickest in the plasmasphere and thinnest on the surface. Where there are solids, Aether is converted to sustain it. Don’t make this harder than it already is for the monkeys.

⁹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7gHglxUMRI4>

¹⁰⁰ A tough distinction, to be sure. But sources emit, while collisions eject (even if they become sources).

¹⁰¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DTaXfbvGf8E>

¹⁰² <https://disk.yandex.ru/i/FnUkHxwI5C5EIg>

- *“So-called magnetic attraction which does not exist.”* ~ a preposterous extraordinary claim that requires extraordinary evidence.
- *“It’s blatantly obvious now what matter is.”* Agree: **charge**.
But you think it’s light. Light is a circuit and circuits distribute charge. So which is simpler? Charge is the simplest of all. At the root of energy-mass is charge. At the root of all of the PEMF and PEMC is charge. Aether is charged. All the things are charge relativities and these relationships are where fields come from.
- *“People misunderstand dielectricity, which of course is counterspatial increasing inertia and acceleration”* Maybe, but then you need energy for this acceleration, and then that source itself needs a source for energy, and so on. So you need a system like Dual Direction Entropy and Cosmic Rearrangement to work this. It’d be interesting to look into Weber and get his opinion because Steinmetz is not the end all be all of electromagnetism. No one, not even Tesla, is. Not Maxwell or Heaviside or Distinti or Thornhill. And definitely not Wheeler or Careaga.
- *“Lightning is a dielectric discharge”* ...In the same but opposite way as it is an electrical discharge...
- *“Scientists ... have extreme difficulty in defining potential, and defining an energy field at all, if you believe me, ask them.”* No I agree that they have trouble, but that doesn’t mean they cannot or have not defined potential. I covered it in the paper. Again: don’t make it harder than it really is.
- *“Even JJ Thompson...”* again: Authority Fallacy. And not even that great an authority, in my opinion.
- *“If you think that’s crazy, even Nikola Tesla said...”* again: Authority Fallacy. We have to keep Tesla, great as he was and is, in his place in the PEMC history. There were other geniuses, as well, not the least of which Irving Langmuir¹⁰³, who won the Nobel for discovering covalent bonds.
- *“There’s no such thing as a charge carrying particle (electron)”*
OK, prove it. Because we have the mass-energy measurement and we have application after application built around it.
- *“There never meant to be big words. I always take offense to people saying I try to use big words to sound smart.”* Ken I hope you’re not too offended with my playful paper. The PEM community loves you and is fascinated by you. But let’s not mince words here, you pontificate like a plenipotentiary with superfluous vernacular of the troglodytic English dialectic. Just speak simpler, sometimes. The audience shouldn’t have to join a mental occult to understand your meaning. That’s why I put out FAQ’s¹⁰⁴, memos¹⁰⁵, and such. Expand your meaning.
- *“If you think there are big words here, I counter to you that there is not.”* Fight with reality all you want. It’s okay to say science is traditionally a Noble pursuit of the more intelligent, and capable. Most of your audience is incapable of remotely sifting through

¹⁰³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/langmuir>

¹⁰⁴ https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS

¹⁰⁵

https://www.academia.edu/40069702/The_Electric_Universe_Memo_For_Plasma_Electromagnetic_and_Diffusion_Catastrophic_Cosmologies_EPEMC_An_Electric_View_Community_Publication

EPEMC :: Opinion Editorial
 Unified Aether Field Series

your ideas. I'd like to see you respond to Distinti's debunk of you. In the following table, are the three most important videos related to Ken Wheelerism. Two are his, and one is R. Distinti's. Also there is a video of Distinti's Unified Aether model.

- “[electricity’s] not a thing in [and of] itself.” Yes, same as anything else. But since other things have ideas and places in and of themselves, so does electricity.
- “I hope you like this, I promised it. Here it is. I dare you to refute it.”
The point is not to refute, but to critique in a positive way and correct or construct it.
- “You might complain, but you won’t be able to refute it”
I leave that for the audience to determine.

Table 1 - Ken Wheeler Vs. Robert Distinti¹⁰⁶

Figures 29 - 32 ; Ken and Distinti's 'battles' of ideas.

¹⁰⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/r-distinti>

Conclusion¹⁰⁷

In general I want to thank Ken for the video, and for the invitation to reply to him. I'd love him to join the Ancient Kentucke Historical Association¹⁰⁸ and join me on a Hidden KY (www.hiddendestinationsky.com) hike or fengshui hike to see the electro-geological¹⁰⁹ sites. I hope even within this county itself, he'd like to review the Mt. Horeb site¹¹⁰ and see my work on the C-henge's antenna behaviors¹¹¹, and we could really have some great symbiotic discussions. Hopefully he's not offended, because it isn't meant in offense. He requested it. After all, at least someone is listening and really considering his ideas. He should also come, as he has an invitation to the PEM World Expo (conference) in August. He could carpool with me. :)

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

¹⁰⁷ 'Imagine that you and I have a disagreement, and you get the better of me, rather than me getting the better of you, does this mean that you are automatically right and I am automatically wrong? Suppose I get the better of you, does it follow that I am automatically right and you are therefore wrong? Is it really that one of us is right and the other wrong? Or are we both right and both wrong? Neither you nor I can really know and other people are even more in the dark. So who can we ask to give us the right answer? Should you ask someone who thinks you are right? But how then can that person give a fair answer? Should we ask someone who thinks I am right? But then if he agrees with me, how can he make a fair judgement? Then again, should we ask someone who agrees with both of us? But again, if he agrees with both of us, how can he make a true judgement? Should we ask someone who disagrees with both of us? But here again, if he disagrees with both of us, how can he make an honest judgement? It is clear that neither you, I nor anyone else can make decisions like this amongst ourselves. So should we wait for someone else to turn up? 'To wait for one voice to bring it all together is as pointless as waiting for no one. Bring all things together under the Equality of Heaven, allow their process of change to go on unimpeded, and learn to grow old. What do I mean by bringing everything together under the Equality of Heaven? With regard to what is right and wrong, I say not being is being and being is not being. But let us not get caught up in discussing this. Forget about life, forget about worrying about right and wrong. Plunge into the unknown and the endless and find your place there!' (sic)

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/ancientkentucky/>

¹⁰⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology>

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph Part 2

¹¹¹ Ibid. pp. 11-17